

Study of Lebbekanin D—A New Saponin of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth. Flowers

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Lebbekanin D, a new triterpenic saponin has been isolated from the flowers of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth. On acid hydrolysis it gave echinocystic acid as sapogenin and glucose, galactose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose as sugars which are present in the molar ratio of 2:2:5:3:3 determined as alditol acetates by G.L.C. It has two sugar chains one at C-28 carboxyl and another at C-3 hydroxyl groups. The flowers have also been found to contain β -sitosterol.

ALBIZZIA *lebbek* Benth. commonly known as 'Siris' in Hindi is a large deciduous tree with an umbrella shaped crown, grows throughout India and flowers once in a year in March/April. It belongs to the family Leguminosae and sub-family Mimoseae. The albizzias have been reported to be a rich source for saponin and sapogenin contents¹. Various parts of this plant have been studied for the saponin and sapogenin contents and have recently been reviewed².

Varshney *et al* have studied various parts of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth. for the saponins. The seeds have been found to contain a mixture of two saponins named as Lebbekanin A and Lebbekanin B. Lebbekanin A on acid hydrolysis yielded echinocystic acid as genin and glucose, galactose, arabinose, xylose, fucose and rhamnose as sugars (5:1:1:1:1:2)³.

Lebbekanin B has been found to be a glycoside of oleanolic acid with four sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose⁴.

The pods have been found to contain a single saponin named as Lebbekanin C which on acid hydrolysis gave echinocystic acid as a genin and glucose and rhamnose as sugars (1:1)².

The flowers of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth. have earlier been studied and reported to contain a glycoside of quercetin and a saponin of echinocystic acid⁵. As no work seems to have been done on the glycosidic part of the saponin of flowers, therefore, this work has been taken up.

The flowers of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth. collected from local campus were dried and extracted with petroleum ether (60°-80°). The petroleum ether extract was chromatographed on silica gel and has been found to be a mixture of three components. One of the components present in major quantity

Fig. 1: G.L.C. curve of alditol acetates of sugars.

has been separated by column chromatography and identified as β -sitosterol by m.p., m.m.p. and comparison of I.R. spectrum with the authentic sample. The other component has been identified as quercetin

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Table 1

Fractions	Solvent	Substance
1- 4	Petroleum ether	Single spot β -sitosterol
5- 7	CHCl ₃ :MeOH:H ₂ O (65:35:10)	Two spots, one major and one minor β -sitosterol and saponin.
8-14	-do-	Single spot Saponin
15-17	-do-	Two spots Saponin-sugar
18-20	-do-	Single spot Sugar

and the third was present in traces and may be some colouring matter.

The petroleum ether exhausted flowers were extracted with ethanol a number of times and the ethanolic extract on concentration yielded a syrupy mass which on treatment with various solvents¹, gave a dark brown gummy mass which was dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol and precipitated in large volume of acetone† a number of times to yield a light brown powder which gave all the tests for saponins. On T.L.C. it showed three spots, one major and two trace spots. Therefore, the saponin mixture was separated by column chromatography on silica gel (Table 1). Fractions 8 to 14 gave a T.L.C. pure saponin named as Lebbekinin D.

Lebbekinin D on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* sulphuric acid gave a genin identified as echinocystic acid by m.p., T.L.C. and I.R. spectrum with authentic sample. The hydrolysate after neutralization has been found to contain a mixture of five sugars identified as glucose, galactose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose by paper chromatography, T.L.C. and G.L.C (Fig. 1) of their alditol acetate derivatives³ as glucose:galactose:arabinose:xylose:rhamnose (2:2:5:3:3).

Lebbekinin D on alkaline hydrolysis with 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide by refluxing for 6 hr gave a prosapogenin and an oligosaccharide showing the presence of an ester linkage (i.e. attachment of sugars) i.e. at C-28 COOH group. The attachment of sugars at C-16 OH group is not possible due to its strongly hindered position. Therefore the sugars are attached at C-3 OH group (which is the most common position in the case of triterpenic saponins) and at C-28 COOH group. Therefore the following

structure has tentatively been suggested for Lebbekinin D.

$R' + R'' =$ Glucose:galactose:arabinose:xylose:rhamnose (2:2:5:3:3)

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† Acetone extract gave a glycoside of quercetin⁵.